

Title

Automated, Self-Directed & Intelligent Learning Bots - Using Reinforcement Learning and Word Embedded Vectors To Gather Knowledge From The Internet

Name

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Abstract

The Internet is the biggest repository of knowledge-material ever amassed. Humans have gotten good at leveraging this resource for all their knowledge-data needs. We rely on search engines, wikis, and linked references multiple times a day to answer our questions and guide our lives. Artificial intelligence can do all of this just as well, maybe even better as it doesn't suffer from attention-span, focus or bias limitations. The challenge is in automating the interaction and understanding of this data source in a comprehensive way. By combining reinforcement learning and word-vector embedding, we can build smart, self-adjusting tools to gather very specific knowledge data sets with more precision than a simple search engine, and with the tireless energy only computers can afford. Leveraging the Euclidean distance from word-embedded vectors we can create a reward system to guide a reinforcement q-learning model to recognize useful knowledge assets and ignore the rest.

Tools

This talk uses practical examples in the Python programming language to illustrate the topic at hand. A beginner with some exposure to the Python programming language and an interest in machine learning and artificial intelligence will be able to follow and reproduce the examples shared.

Keywords

Word Embedded Vectors, Reinforcement Learning, AI, Python, Automated Technologies

Biography

Manuel Amunategui is VP of Data Science at SpringML, a startup offering operations, finance, healthcare, marketing, lead generation and sales predictive analytics using Google Cloud TensorFlow and Salesforce enterprise solutions. Prior to that he was a data scientist at Providence Health and Services, a quantitative developer at Group One Trading, a large equity-options market-making firm present on all major US exchanges and a software developer at Microsoft. He holds master degrees in Predictive Analytics and International Administration. He is a data science advocate, blogger/vlogger (amunategui.github.io) and a trainer on [Udemy.com](https://www.udemy.com/) and O'Reilly Media, and technical reviewer at Packt Publishing.